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Deliverable D1.4.2: Models of crisis concepts and dynamics

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Crises can be seen as naturally occurring socio-physical systems with complex dynamics and appreciable impact on human life and well being. Being able to abstract and logically correlate the results of such an abstraction, i.e. create models, could conceivably offer insight into the hidden underlying causalities, which may be used to mitigate the effects of future crises. That said, the sheer complexity of a crisis, the diversity of factors affecting it, the uncontrollable power of natural phenomena governing it, and the parallel evolution of many interacting processes result in a considerable degree of indeterminacy, which is not directly amenable to modelling. To this, one should add the continuous nature of the dynamics of a crisis, as opposed to the discrete nature of the available product and process models based on computer-aided architectures producing the so-called enterprise, process, data or organisational models.

Despite these difficulties, there is a considerable amount of research involved in modelling crises, with the aim to produce IT tools to help evaluate scenarios of possible action and select semi-optimal options among various alternatives. A crisis is characterised by the unpredictability of its time evolution (dynamics), which makes this part quite difficult to model. On the other hand, the actors involved in a crisis are relatively well-defined: response organisations with known structure and hierarchies, equipment of varying functionality, different forms of infrastructure and people under relatively known social organisation schemes. This part, consisting of relatively “static” aspects, is directly amenable to semantic modelling aiming at the creation of uniform terminologies and dictionaries, thus directly benefiting semantic interoperability and integration among relevant IT systems and tools. Along these lines, a short survey of the modelling challenges and efforts inspired by the needs of crisis management is presented in chapter 2.

Within the limitations listed above, we have utilised the findings of deliverables D1.1, D1.2 and D1.3 to formulate a model/typology of crises and the associated concepts and actions in chapter 3. Given that the creation of an all-encompassing model of a crisis is generally not feasible, we have offered a high level description of the features and dynamics of crises as described in WP1, based on a well-known modelling method, the Unified Modelling Language.

At the present stage of the model, we have confined ourselves to objects and object classes, stakeholders (actors, a special class of objects), and activities. The aim is to offer abstractions for selected parts of the material of WP1 which depict structure (via object classes and objects) and behaviour (via activities) during crises. The initial idea in this deliverable is to view a crisis as an object in an object-oriented environment. Starting from our main interest, a CRISIS is a class of objects which can be described by common characteristics and parameters (attributes), and which, upon assignment of specific values to these attributes, can generate its various specific objects, such as: the Katrina Hurricane, the Boston Bombings, the Heat Wave in France and so on, as studied in WP1.

Objects, as abstractions of the real world have inherent dynamics and are also transformed by processes and activities which act upon them. These object transformers can be modelled in various ways, even in UML, but what we have chosen here is to model them as activities. In this way, the course of the evolution of a crisis is via a set of activities executed in sequence or in parallel or both. We have isolated here the most important activities related to crises as presented in WP1. The so constructed high level model was subsequently coded

using a UML compliant IT tool (Enterprise Architect) so as to check consistency and to provide a uniform way of presentation. Results can be seen in chapter 4.

Finally, communications challenges in crises are abundant in various forms and have been analysed by the partners in many parts of COSMIC. Communication also affects the course of the crisis itself and its impact. The difficulty is however that it is not a well-defined process which is amenable to modelling. Here, we have isolated the tabulated challenges and prescribed processes for communication during crises, as they appear in our deliverables, which may form part of a future model, although, at this stage, we are not able to express those in a consistent semi-formal way.

1 INTRODUCTION

Models are used in almost all aspects of human activity as ways of separating important features of an evolving situation or a phenomenon in nature. These features, which may be also changing in time (dynamic), can provide insight into the underlying causalities or physical laws which determine the course of the situation or the phenomenon. In other words, models are mechanisms of abstraction serving defined purposes and mapping reality into logically connected entities.

Crises can be seen as naturally occurring socio-physical systems with complex dynamics and appreciable impact on human life and well being. Being able to abstract and logically correlate the results of such an abstraction, i.e. create models, could conceivably offer insight into the hidden underlying causalities, which may be used to mitigate the effects of future crises. That said, the sheer complexity of a crisis, the diversity of factors affecting it, the uncontrollable power of natural phenomena governing it, and the parallel evolution of many interacting processes result in a considerable degree of indeterminacy, which is not directly amenable to modelling. To this, one should add the continuous nature of the dynamics of a crisis, as opposed to the discrete nature of the available product and process models based on computer-aided architectures producing the so-called enterprise, process, data or organisational models.

Despite these difficulties, models have been applied in certain areas of crisis management. There is a considerable amount of research involved in modelling crises, with the aim to produce IT tools to help evaluate scenarios of possible action and select semi-optimal options among various alternatives. Such findings frequently help shape the guidelines along which response organisations act, usually referred to under the collective name of “Standard Operating Procedures”. These prescribe the way under which organisations operate and usually include “the mandate, the hierarchy and a way of action prescribed according to a taxonomy of conditions.”¹

As crises affect objects of the real world, models must be able to represent not only actions in time (dynamics) but also actors (persons at various roles), state of real world objects and relations among them all. In other words, a model is a time series (dynamics) of time-frozen snapshots of all involved entities and their relations. A close equivalent in IT terms is the triad process-structure-semantic which characterises the correspondence between the real world and the virtual world. In fact, and in accordance to our comments above, the unpredictability of a crisis makes the process (time evolution or dynamics) part quite difficult to model. On the other hand, the actors involved in a crisis are relatively well-defined: response organisations with known structure and hierarchies, equipment of varying functionality, different forms of infrastructure and people under relatively known social organisation schemes. It is not surprising therefore that crisis models have by enlarge concentrated on those “static” aspects. In particular, there has been considerable research work on semantic models of crisis concepts, in an attempt to create uniform terminologies and dictionaries and to help semantic interoperability and integration among IT systems.

¹ COSMIC Deliverable D3.3.1 “First report on the strategic use of emerging communication technologies for crisis stakeholders”

2 TOWARDS MODELLING CRISES

COSMIC lies at the crossroads of social media and crisis management, and so do the associated semantics issues. Corresponding models also affect then both: semantic models for social media and semantic models for crises. Both aspects have been analysed in Deliverable D3.2.2². Here we only concentrate on semantic models of crises and borrow parts of this analysis.

As crises use a relatively limited terminology, ontologies are suitable tools for modelling the relevant concepts and the relations among them. Researchers in the European project Disaster 2.0³ surveyed a large number of such ontologies against 11 areas of informational concepts (including resources, processes, people, damage, type of disaster and others) and arrived at the following table (also included in D3.2.2) of originally designed for crisis management ontologies.

Table 1. Relevant crisis ontologies, aims and concepts they represent⁴

Representative Crisis Ontologies	Types of Crisis Management Systems aimed for	Requirements of Information Representation
SOKNOS	Information integration for resource planning	Categorisation of damages and resources, deploy regulations defining the relations between them
SIADDEX	Planning under uncertainty for decision support	Taxonomy of resources, legal information on the use of resources, operational targets and tasks for specific crisis scenarios, representation of uncertainty (temporal, resource and location)
ISyCri	Crisis response coordination	Categories of entities affected by crises, the treatment system, the crisis description
MOAC, HXL	Humanitarian disaster response and relief	Classification of damages, crises, response activities and resources; geo location about displaced persons
WB-OS	Web sites for disaster management	Features, components and information used to create disaster management web sites

The authors note that there is no uniformity of features among the entries of the table: some are formally represented but not publicly available, and coverage of areas is not uniform:

- SOKNOS – resources, damage and disasters (3 areas)
- SIADDEX⁵ – resources, processes and geography (3 areas)
- ISyCri – processes, damages and disasters (3 areas)

² Ioannis Kotsiopoulos, Angelos Yannopoulos, Hayley Watson, Rachel Finn, Rowena Rodrigues, Kush Wadhwa, Alex Papadimitriou, Lemi Baruh, Deliverable 3.2.2, section 2.2.4, “Standardisation of social media data”, COSMIC, 6th November 2014

³ Disaster 2.0 Project, EC Directorate-General Home Affairs, HOME/2010/CIPS/AG/002, <http://www.disaster20.eu>

⁴ Liu S., Brewster C., Shaw D., “Ontologies for Crisis Management: A Review of State of the Art in Ontology Design and Usability”, Proceedings of the 10th International ISCRAM Conference – Baden-Baden, Germany, May 2013, T. Comes, F. Fiedrich, S. Fortier, J. Geldermann and L. Yang, eds., Table 2

⁵ de la Asunción, M., Castillo, L., Fdez-Olivares, J., García-Pérez, O., González, A., Palao, F., “SIADDEX: An interactive knowledge-based planner for decision support in forest fire fighting, AI Commun., 18, 4, 257-268, 2005

- MOAC (Management Of A Crisis)^{6, 7} – resources, processes, damage and disasters (4 areas)
- HXL (Humanitarian eXchange Language)⁸ – damage, geography, organisation and disasters (4 areas)
- WB-OS – processes⁹

Of those, we distinguish two, which are of particular significance and promise for the purposes of COSMIC:

- MOAC, which conforms to de-facto standards developed by the Inter Agency Standing Committee (IASC), the Emergency Shelter Cluster in Haiti, the 3W database¹⁰ and the Ushahidi Haiti Project¹¹, thus having a direct link with social media. In fact, as Carsten Keßler and Chad Hendrix observe¹² the proposal for Crowdsourced Linked Open Data¹³ is the only actual application to date, where information about the Haiti earthquake collected on the Ushahidi platform was organised and made available online, using the Management Of A Crisis (MOAC) vocabulary developed for this purpose.
- HXL, which links to the OGC GeoSPARQL standard for defining geo location vocabularies and which is supported by the UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA). At present, the HXL vocabulary formalises established terminology from the domain, with a focus on humanitarian profile data and core reference data, such as geographic information. The vocabulary is expected to be gradually extended as required, along with its use in relevant applications (see footnote ref⁸).

As concluded in D3.2.2, section 2.2.4, due to a variety of reasons such as the general fragmentation among existing solutions and the lack of consensus across stakeholders, sharing a single domain ontology (model) among different crisis-related IT applications is not feasible. The answer proposed by researchers of Disaster 2.0¹⁴ was to cover identified key interoperability gaps of existing ontologies, by another one created within the project and designed to evolve. It is a formal ontology called DiRes, which describes emergency and disaster events, and the key factors associated with disaster response activities¹⁵. DiRes

⁶ Management Of A Crisis (MOAC) vocabulary, 2012 specification, <http://observedchange.com/moac/ns>

⁷ Benaben, F., Hanachi, C., Lauras, M., Couget, P., Chapurlat, V., “A Metamodel and its Ontology to Guide Crisis Characterization and its Collaborative Management”, Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on Information Systems for Crisis Response and Management (ISCRAM 2008), Washington, DC, USA, 189-196, 2008

⁸ Carsten Keßler, Chad Hendrix, “The Humanitarian eXchange Language: Coordinating Disaster Response with Semantic Web Technologies”, Semantic Web Journal 1 (2009) 1–5, IOS Press, 2013, http://www.semantic-web-journal.net/system/files/swj537_0.pdf

⁹ This ontology contains web elements which a government website should have so as to serve disaster management. From that point of view it covers the process area as relates to the way (process) of building relevant government web sites.

¹⁰ Who does What Where (3W), Contact Management Directory, UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA), <http://3w.unocha.org/WhoWhatWhere>

¹¹ <http://www.ushahidi.com/2011/04/19/ushahidi-haiti-project-evaluation-final-report>

¹² Carsten Keßler, Chad Hendrix, as above

¹³ Jens Ortman, Minu Limbu, Dong Wang, and Tomi Kauppinen, “Crowdsourcing Linked Open Data for Disaster Management”, in Rolf Grütter, Dave Kolas, Manolis Koubarakis, Dieter Pfoser (eds), Proceedings of Terra Cognita 2011, Workshop at the 10th International Semantic Web Conference, (ISWC2011), volume 798 of CEUR Workshop Proceedings, Bonn, Germany, October 2011.

¹⁴ Disaster 2.0 Project, EC Directorate-General Home Affairs, HOME/2010/CIPS/AG/002, <http://www.disaster20.eu>

¹⁵ Ibid., <http://www.disaster20.eu/dires>

defines terms relating to disasters (what has happened), operations (what can be done), people and organisation (who are involved and take actions), resources (what are needed and used), time and location (when and where), and the damage that a disaster has caused. DiRes specialises the Friend of a Friend (FOAF) ontology¹⁶, the W3C Organisation ontology¹⁷ and the Open Geospatial Consortium GeoSPARQL ontology¹⁸ in order to describe correspondingly people from different governmental agencies and organisations, the origin place and boundary of a disaster event, and the check-in location of a disaster response operation by first responders and aid agencies.

The specification of DiRes is still evolving and its wider acceptance is dependent on a variety of factors ranging from policy (for example the fragmentation observed in the EU) to ease of use and to added adoption by governmental and non-governmental organisations.¹⁹

2.1 ADDING PROCESS MODELS

Besides relying on a static structured “picture” of concepts and relations, more complete enterprise models combining process and semantics have been proposed. In these cases, the use of a modelling language, such as for example a general purpose one (UML and others) or one specifically designed for the particular domain (crisis) is usually necessary. Referring to Table 1, ISyCri and MOAC include process models in their specification. For example, ISyCri uses a UML metamodel for crisis and response process management on ontologies described via OWL-DL.²⁰

Figure 1. An excerpt of the emergency management and domain ontology of De Nicola and Villani²¹

Finally, it is worth noting a recent attempt on crisis modelling directed at emergency management scenarios, which proposes a framework for automatic support to modellers to enable models of unlikely events and their management. Using the domain-specific language

¹⁶ <http://xmlns.com/foaf/spec>

¹⁷ <http://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-org>

¹⁸ <http://www.opengeospatial.org/standards/geosparql>

¹⁹ This short description of the DiRes ontology has also been included in COSMIC Deliverable D3.3.2 under section 3.3 on semantic interoperability

²⁰ W3C, Web Ontology Language – Description Logics (OWL-DL), 2009, <http://www.w3.org/TR/owl-guide>

²¹ Antonio De Nicola, Maria Luisa Villani, “Creative Modelling of Emergency Management Scenarios”, European CIIP Newsletter, Vol. 8, No. 3, 2014

CEML (Crisis and Emergency Modelling Language)^{22, 23} and a specifically built emergency management domain ontology (see figure above for a representative sample) the method the authors propose²⁴ starts from the selection of predefined design patterns and, by means of mini-stories semantic binding and composition and data assignment, produces concrete emergency management scenario models. The interesting idea behind this approach is that the experienced practitioner and his domain knowledge can be paired with automated help into formalising this via an enterprise model which incorporates process as well as knowledge parts.

²² D'Agostino G., De Nicola A., Di Pietro A., Vicoli G., Villani M.L., Rosato V., "A Domain Specific Language for the Description and the Simulation of Systems of Interacting Systems", *Advances in Complex Systems*, Vol. 15, Suppl. No. 1; 2012

²³ Antonio De Nicola, Giordano Vicoli, Maria Luisa Villani, "A Rule-based Approach for Modelling Behaviour in Crisis and Emergency Scenarios", in "Enterprise Interoperability V", *Proceedings of the I-ESA Conferences Volume 5*, 2012, pp 93-103.

²⁴ Antonio De Nicola, Maria Luisa Villani, "Creative Modelling of Emergency Management Scenarios", *European CIIP Newsletter*, Vol. 8, No. 3, 2014

3 MODELLING CRISES IN COSMIC

For the purposes of COSMIC, the aim is to utilise the findings of deliverables D1.1, D1.2 and D1.3 to formulate a model/typology of crisis situations to help in the identification of features such as information and communication needs, infrastructural bottlenecks, security priorities and major stakeholders associated with each type of crisis. Given the difficulties stated above, the creation of an all encompassing model of a crisis is generally not feasible, at least within the resources and mandate of a Support Action such as COSMIC. What we attempt to do however, is to offer a way to formalise features and dynamics of crises as described in WP1, based on a well-known modelling method, the Unified Modelling Language.

The **Unified Modelling Language™ - UML** - is OMG's²⁵ “most-used specification, and the way the world models not only application structure, behaviour, and architecture, but also business process and data structure.”²⁶

At the present stage of the model, we do not use the full range of constructs available, but confine ourselves to:

- Objects and object classes
- Actors (a special class of objects), and
- Activities

Our basic choice is to offer abstractions for selected parts of the material of WP1 which depict:

- Structure (via object classes and objects)
- Behaviour (via activities)

during crises.

3.1 MODELLING CONSTRUCTS

The initial idea in this deliverable is to view a crisis as an object in an object-oriented environment. A brief explanation of objects, classes and their main properties is given below; the interested reader can refer to a wealth of bibliography.²⁷ Objects are models of things of the real world which have a function, contain parameters (attributes), and are parts of collections of objects with similar characteristics, called classes. A useful characteristic of an object is inheritance, where objects of the same class can transfer common characteristics (e.g. attributes) to new subordinate objects created within the same class.

Starting from our main interest, a CRISIS is a class of objects which can be described by common characteristics and parameters (attributes), and which, upon assignment of specific values to these attributes can generate its various specific objects, such as: the Katrina Hurricane, the Boston Bombings, the Heat Wave in France and so on, as studied in WP1. This process of realising an object by specifying values in the parameters of the relevant class is called “instantiation” in the object-oriented jargon.

²⁵ Object Management Group (OMG), <http://www.omg.org>

²⁶ <http://www.uml.org>

²⁷ For example: Abadi, M., Cardelli, L., “A theory of Objects”, Springer 1998

Objects, as abstractions of the real world have inherent dynamics and are also transformed by processes and activities which act upon them. These object transformers can be modelled in various ways, even in UML, but what we have chosen here is to model them as activities. In this way, the course of the evolution of a crisis is via a set of activities executed in sequence or in parallel or both. We have isolated here the most important activities related to crises as presented in WP1.

Following the above constructs, our basic building blocks for modelling crises are:

- Classes of objects
- Activities on objects

The more detailed description of the classes and the activities is shown in what follows. Subordinate attributes or activities are shown using indentations. All descriptions are extracts from WP1 deliverables with appropriate references when needed.

For the second part of this deliverable we will populate the model with additional constructs and detail, and we will also try to express our model in terms of an IT-supported tool.

A general reference map of the concepts used is shown in the following figure.

Figure 2. Bibliographical map of main concepts in COSMIC deliverable documents

The essential elements of a model for crises are described below as objects (classes) and activities, as extracted from the deliverable documents of WP1.

3.2 CLASSES

We first describe the class of crises with their related attributes referring to impact, evolution, phases, and type of crisis as presented in D1.1 of COSMIC, followed by the classes of the media and the stakeholders. The figure below summarises the classes considered.

Figure 3. Classes of objects used in the model

3.2.1 Detailed description

<p>Class Class name: CRISIS</p> <p>Attributes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Impact <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cross-border • High impact • Low impact • Short-term • Long-term • Physical <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizens' health • Critical infrastructure damage <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transportation • Power-Energy • Water • Agriculture • Authorities & public services (incl. schools) • Communication networks • Business <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local business • Heritage • Tourism • Insurance
--

- Government
 - Local
 - National
 - Environment
- Social
 - Psychosocial
 - Sociodemographic
 - Socioeconomic
 - Sociopolitical
- Type of evolution
 - Flash
 - Creeping
- Phases (timeline, D1.3, p9)
 - Preparation
 - Prevention
 - Risk communication
 - Externally
 - Internally
 - Warning
 - Prevention
 - Risk communication
 - Externally
 - Internally
 - Response
 - Repression
 - Crisis communication
 - Externally
 - Internally
 - Recovery
- Type of crisis
 - Flood
 - Extreme temperature
 - Storm
 - Wildfire
 - Earthquake
 - Man-made
 - Technological & accidental hazards
 - Blackout
 - Hazardous material incidents
 - Nuclear power plants
 - Terrorist acts
 - Explosions
 - Biological threats
 - Chemical threats
 - Cyber attacks
 - Nuclear blasts
 - Radiological dispersion devices

Class

Class name: MEDIA (Communication)

Attributes:

- Risk Communication
 - Externally
 - Internally
- Crisis Communication
 - Externally
 - Internally
- Cross-border

Class

Class name: Stakeholders (Actors)

Subordinate classes:

- Citizens (individuals)
- Society and Communities (collections of citizens)
 - Resilience
 - Economic development
 - Social capital
 - Sufficient information and communication
 - Community competences
- Organisations
 - Type 1: Established organisations (with regular tasks and old structures)
 - Bilateral organisations
 - Civil protection
 - Police
 - Fire service
 - Health service
 - Multilateral organisations
 -
 - Type 2: Expanding organisations (with regular tasks and new structures)
 - Civil society or non-governmental organisations (CSOs/NGOs)
 - Local
 - International
 - Type 3: Extending organisations (with non-regular tasks and old structures)
 - Type 4: Emergent groups (with new tasks and new structures)

As an example, we show the instantiations (objects) of one of the classes subordinate to the class of stakeholders, namely that of Type 1 organisations, as realised by the State of California and the Italian National Service for Civil Protection.

Subordinate class instantiation: Organisations Type 1

Subordinate class name: Stakeholder agencies of the State of California for heatwaves

Owner: California Governor's Office of Emergency Services²⁸, D1.2, p. 65
 Members and explanation of roles:

Department/ Agency	Responsibility
California State Warning Center (CSWC) (Cal EMA)	Statewide emergency notification
California Emergency Management Agency (Cal EMA)	Emergency management – all SEMS/NIMS functions – recovery programs
Cal EMA Law Enforcement Branch	Law enforcement / coroner operations
California Department of Aging (CDA)	Provide communication and assistance to senior and caregivers services
Business, Transportation & Housing Agency (BT&H)	Loan guarantees for farm & agriculture related enterprises
California National Guard (CNG)	Logistical support – armories
Community Services & Development (CSD)	Community Service Block Grants (CSBG), Low Income Home Energy Assistance Program (LIHEAP) – migrant programs
Department of Developmental Services (DDS)	Provide communication and assistance to Regional Centers and Developmental Centers who provide direct services and assistance to people with developmental disabilities; Advise Cal EMA on the needs of people with developmental disabilities
Department of Food and Agriculture (CDFA)	Agricultural livestock - pet issues - fairground facilities - link to agricultural commissioners & growers
Department of Health Care Services (DHCS)	Medi-Cal
Department of Public Health (CDPH)	Public health programs
Department of Housing & Community Development (HCD)	Housing programs
Department of Mental Health (DMH)	Crisis Counseling Immediate Services, Crisis Counseling Regular Program
Department of Rehabilitation (DOR)	Provide communication and assistance to the disability community
Department of Social Services (DSS)	CalWORKs cash aid (including immediate need), food stamp benefits (including expedited service and/or disaster food stamp benefits), food commodities programs, and coordination of state resource in support of local government. Oversight of community facilities responsible for the health and safety of vulnerable populations, and ARC shelters.
Department of Transportation (CalTrans)	Transportation – public works
Emergency Medical Services Authority (EMSA)	Emergency medical care
Employment Development Department (EDD)/ Workforce & Labor Development Agency	Unemployment insurance, disaster unemployment assistance, job training services
Franchise Tax Board (FTB)	Activating the 1-800 number call center

²⁸ California Governor's Office of Emergency Services, “Heat”, 2010. <http://www.calema.ca.gov/planningandpreparedness/pages/heat.aspx>

Subordinate class instantiation: Organisations Type 1

Subordinate class name: National agencies for national level emergencies

Owner: National Service for Civil Protection - Italy²⁹, D1.3, p. 19

Members and explanation of roles:

NOTES

As found in D1.1. p. 103, the strength and effectiveness of community responses are determined by different factors. Sufficient resources (economic, natural) are crucial to get access to the groups that can make a difference. It is also important that there is a culture that ‘permits challenges to authority’. Institutions for facilitating and coordinating responses are

²⁹ Vademecum for Civil Protection, EU Commission, Humanitarian Aid & Civil Protection, found at http://ec.europa.eu/echo/civil_protection/civil/vademecum/it/2-it-1.html#over

important too, as well the political access to the decision-making process for citizens who want to be engaged in.

The four attributes described in the stakeholders class above under “Resilience” are further elaborated on and possibly can contribute to a more detailed class description as shown in the following figure. They influence the level at which a community facilitates its own resilience. An absence of those factors will have a constraining effect on resilience.

Figure 4: Community resilience as a set of networked adaptive qualities.³⁰

3.3 ACTIVITIES

Activities are representative of the dynamics of crises and its particular characteristics. They act on object classes by transforming them in various ways and when in real life (when instantiated) they act on the particular instantiations of classes and subordinate classes, i.e. on objects, such as civilians, response organisations and crises themselves at various stages of evolution. The figure below shows the high level activities that constitute the model.

³⁰ Norris et al., 2007, p. 136.

Figure 5. Activities used in the model

Detailed description of the activities follows as extracted from D1.1.

3.3.1 Individual dynamics during crises

<p>Activity Activity name: Individual dynamics Activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preparation • Warning³¹ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Identification in parallel with media communication ◦ Risk assessment in parallel with media communication ◦ Risk reduction in parallel with media communication ◦ Protective response in parallel with media communication • Response <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Cognitive processes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Intuitive process (in parallel with:)
--

³¹ COSMIC D1.1, page 84: Perry, R.W. and M.K. Lindell (2003). Understanding Citizen Response to Disasters with Implications for Terrorism. *Journal of Contingencies and Crisis Management*. 11(2), pp. 51–52.

- Analytical process
 - Pro-social behaviour
 - Recovery and aftermath
- Object classes acting on:
- Stakeholders
 - Crisis
 - Media

NOTE

The perception of risk among individuals differs widely and is determined by various factors and situations, as shown in D1.1, p. 79.

As simplified graphical representation of the activity in shown in the following figure. The notation is in accordance with the UML activity diagrams. Note that all subordinate activities are shown as individual diagrams. The diagrams are given here as an example of what an IT-supported modelling tool can offer.

Activity diagramme for "Individual Dynamics"

Activity diagramme for sub-activity "Warning"

Activity diagramme for sub-activity "Response"

Activity diagramme for sub-activity "Cognitive Processes"

Figure 6. Activity diagram for "Individual Dynamics" in UML notation

3.3.2 Organisational dynamics during crises

Activity

Activity name: Organisational dynamics

Activities

- Preparation in parallel with media communication
- Response in parallel with media communication
- Recovery and aftermath in parallel with media communication

Object classes acting on:

- Stakeholders
- Crisis
- Media

NOTE

As pointed out in D1.1. p. 92, it is difficult to link the organisational dynamics to the typical crisis situations detailed in Chapter 2 of D1.1. Organisational dynamics, as described in the scientific literature, are quite general and abstract. In fact, it is very likely that all of the organisations (type 1-4) will be present in one of the typical crisis situations in one form or another.”

Also (D1.1. p. 97) it appears to be very difficult to predict what kind of behaviour organisations and groups will exhibit, largely because each crisis situation consists of many different and sometimes distinct variables. As such, citizens and groups are required to respond differently to each new disaster. Nevertheless, it can be argued that the preparation phase will be (mostly) executed by Type 1 organisations (e.g., emergency services, etc.) and the other types of organisations are present in the other phases of each typical crisis situation. Partners have found that it is likely that there will be more Type 2 (e.g., volunteers of the Red Cross), Type 3 (e.g., companies that initiate rescue operations) organisations and emergent groups when a crisis situation is heavier and longer. If emergency agencies are not able to cope with the impact of a particular large-scale disaster, it can be expected that other types of organisations and groups will fill the gap.

The next activity is an instantiation of the previous one, as applied to Emergent Groups.

Activity

Activity name: Organisational dynamics (Emergent Groups)

Activities

- Preparation in parallel with media communication
- Response in parallel with media communication
 - Establishment of emergent groups structure
 - Ensure organizational legitimacy
 - Set up of organisational communication
 - Emergence of a hierarchical leadership structure
 - Establishment of an organic evolving structure
- Recovery and aftermath in parallel with media communication

-
- Object classes acting on:
- Stakeholders
 - Crisis
 - Media

The following are examples of instantiations of the Organisational Dynamics Activity, as applied by various national authorities for various types of crisis.

Activity instantiation: Xenokratis plan³²

Activity name: Organisational dynamics

Owner: Hellenic General Secretariat for Civil Protection, D1.2, p. 31

Activities

- Preparation in parallel with media communication
 - Identify the relevant departments and agencies as well as institutions which direct and coordinate the operational forces at all levels.
 - Provide essential information to the pertinent authorities for the assessment of situations and risks, identification of vulnerable areas and subsequently the drawing up of specific projects within the framework of the basic project "Xenokratis" to deal with the corresponding risks.
 - Guidelines are provided for:
 - the development of strategies and tactics,
 - the proper organisation and equipment of agencies,
 - configuration of an operational philosophy for timely mobilization, motivation, direction and coordination of manpower and resources.
 - Potential logistics capabilities are defined for troubleshooting both operational forces, and the affected citizens.
 - Finally, a communications system is forecasted providing an information flow between all services and agents involved in crisis management.
- Response in parallel with media communication
 - 1st Phase (Usual Readiness): This phase includes measures and actions of the State apparatus, which help prepare for the next phase actions. The first data and information referring to an occurrence or an imminent catastrophic event is evaluated to form a reliable estimate of the event's catastrophic magnitude. Communication systems and data flow channels are activated to support decision making between all relevant stakeholders. Means of civil protection are recorded and checked for adequacy and suitability.
 - 2nd Phase (Increased Readiness): In case information from the previous phase is verified then a wider mobilization of the civil protection mechanism occurs at all levels. All executive and operational services are placed on full alert for the execution of their mission while at the same time taking preventive measures, where necessary.
 - 3rd Phase (Immediate Mobilization/Intervention): After a catastrophic event has occurred, the full civil protection mechanism is activated by the GSCP. Gathering

³² General Secretariat for Civil Protection (originally issued by State Printing Office), 2008.
http://www.gsep.gr/ggpp_cms_files/dynamic/c60463/file/ypapofasi12992003xenokrati_el_GR.pdf

of information about the size and intensity of destruction is followed by an overall evaluation of the situation by the GSCP. Local authorities and civil protection bodies are in constant communication in order to coordinate all actions which will lead to the protection of civilians who managed to avoid injury and the rescue of any civilians who are in need of help.

- Recovery and aftermath in parallel with media communication
 - 4th Phase (Rehabilitation/Assistance): The last phase involves the immediate assistance to the affected population. Damages are evaluated by experts, decisions are made and measures are taken to repair the damage and ensure that similar damages can be prevented in the future.

Object classes acting on:

- Stakeholders
- Crisis
- Media

Subordinate activity instantiation: Earthquake preparation

Subordinate activity name: Preparation in parallel with media communication

Owner: Event³³, D1.2, p. 33

Activities

- Mapping and evaluation of active faults especially those identified near major cities.
- Maintain and enhance a single network of seismograph and accelerographs with dense coverage of Greece and real time data transmission.
- Construct a single accepted speed model for the Greek area (representative of / based on the structure of each region).
- More detailed mapping of intense topographic anomalies in and around the built environment.
- Soil classification and characterization and seismic microzonation, at least for the case of plans for the expansion of a city.
- Perform additional studies of the history of earthquakes due to the long period of recurrence in certain areas (e.g., Kozani, Athens).
- Continuous monitoring and evaluation of seismic activity, and focus on the spatiotemporal progress (further study the features of pre-seismic series).
- Seismic Early Warning System for the safety of network infrastructure utilities (e.g., natural gas) and the safety of industrial facilities (chemical, nuclear, etc.).
- Mapping vulnerability of existing important buildings and financial incentives to reinforce them.
- Creating registry of building manufacturers, quality control building materials.
- Integration of those conclusions in the next update of Anti-seismic Regulation.
- Educating citizens, with priority given to pupils and integrating relevant courses at school.

³³ The Seismological Laboratory of the University of Athens, the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Forecasting of Earthquakes and the Geodynamics National Observatory of Athens organised an event entitled "10 years of Athens earthquake: experiences and lessons learned," which took place on the 3rd and 4th of December 2009, in the "Aristotle" auditorium of the Physics Department at the University of Athens. The purpose of the event was to review the experience and lessons learned from the Athens earthquake and other major earthquakes as well as to suggest future actions which could eliminate or at least minimise the dangers that are present when earthquakes strike.

Subordinate activity instantiation: Preparation for crisis

Subordinate activity name: Preparation in parallel with media communication

Owner: Rizzuto & Maloney³⁴, D1.2, p. 49

Activities

- **Plan beyond the organisational boundaries.**

COMMENT: Though the planning of the internal operations can be good (and that was the case by the most of the organisations involved in the preparation for Katrina), other actors can frustrate your good efforts with inadequate planning. Only when the most people show self-sufficiency in the period before storm and flood, specific help and support organisations can focus on the groups that really need their help.

- **Develop and exercise crisis contingencies.**

COMMENT: Different crisis management teams, like for crisis communication, decision-making and search and rescue, need to have a close collaboration. Firstly a common experience can strengthen the further the common approach; double efforts will be minimized. Secondly, by training together (as a team), different actors will learn from each other. These exercises must be taken place periodically and during an evaluation the different team members must be confronted with possible improvements for the future.

- **Embed leadership throughout the organisation.**

COMMENT: Good crisis response needs decision-making on different places within the organisation. As there is no time to waste when a disaster occurs, the distribution of power and influence between different actors enlarges the reaction time. That important knowledge for the response phase highlights the importance of allocating new responsibilities to existing roles. Employees have to get the opportunities to develop their (leadership) skills; if they have not, they won't take responsibilities.

- **Invest in employee-employer commitment.**

COMMENT: A lack of trust delays processes within an organisation, also in the preparation on and the response to crises or disasters. Trust is a key component for good communications, intra-organisational collaborations and decentralized decision-making.³⁵ It can create an atmosphere of solidarity and of doing a job together.

- **Build a culture that can readily adapt to change.**

COMMENT: Of course, structures and formalized procedures are important to deal with the direct consequences of a crisis. But without the abilities to respond to new, unexpected and dynamic circumstances, it seems to be impossible to react on new situations. Like Edmondson, Bohmer and Pisano³⁶ stress, leaders of organizations who promote dynamic and broad-minded attitudes, and who see crises more as opportunities instead as only as threats; they are more able to cope with such non-daily situations.

³⁴ Rizzuto, Tracey E. & Maloney, Laura K., Organizing Chaos: Crisis Management in the Wake of Hurricane Katrina, *Professional Psychology: Research and Practice*, Vol. 39, Issue 1, 2008, pp. 77-85.

³⁵ Mishra, A., Organizational responses to crisis: The centrality of trust, *Roderick Kramer & Thomas Tyler (Eds.), Trust in organizations*, pp. 261-287, Newbury Park, CA: Sage, 1996.

³⁶ Edmondson, A., R. Bohmer & G. Pisano, Disrupted routines: Team learning and new technology implementation in hospitals, *Administrative Science Quarterly*, Issue 46, 2001, pp. 685-716.

Subordinate activity instantiation: Preparation for flood

Subordinate activity name: Preparation in parallel with media communication

Owner: National French floods management plan³⁷, D1.2, p. 52

Activities

- **Proper urban development in high flood risk prone areas.**
COMMENT: Through restrictions for building in areas with a more than an average flood risk and an all-embracing plan for the design and implementation of prevention works, the authorities try to optimise the qualities of the coastal defence and minimise the danger for the future. Furthermore the different coastal municipalities and cities had to prepare their own prevention plans.
- **Improve floods forecasting, monitoring and early warning systems**
COMMENT: The actor involved in this pillar of the management plan is the French meteorological institute. With a special forecasting service, on the basis of sea and waves forecasts and the implementation of a system with the emergency colours green, orange and red citizens can be informed better about the risks in their region. Also the monitoring of the water level in the different rivers has to be improved.
- **Dam system reinforcements.**
COMMENT: In the period between 2011 and 2016, 1200 kilometre of dams at the coastline will be checked and improved. The same applies for the hydraulic works safety control services.
- **Development of a risk management culture at all levels.**
COMMENT: All the municipal emergency plans had to include a specific chapter with a focus on the prevention for storms and floods and their possible consequences. Furthermore there is a moral commitment for the authorities to create awareness among the population, and show examples where they can arrange to mitigate the associated vulnerabilities.

Subordinate activity instantiation: Preparation for a heatwave

Subordinate activity name: Preparation in parallel with media communication

Owner: French Ministry of Social Affairs and Health³⁸, D1.2, p. 60

Activities

- **Level 1 - seasonal surveillance**
COMMENT: Seasonal surveillance, while on Level 1, is a green colour on the map of weather vigilance. This level is automatically activated from June 1 to August 31 of each year. In case of early or late heat, seasonal surveillance can be activated before June 1 or extended after August 31. During this summer period measures that are usually taken include the following:
 - verification of operational systems,
 - establishment of a meteorological and health monitoring device and
 - activating the national emergency platform phone number.

³⁷ PPRD (Prevention, preparedness response to natural and man-made disasters) South Programme, 2011, <http://www.preventionweb.net/english/professional/contacts/v.php?id=6147>

³⁸ Les niveaux d'alerte du Plan national canicule - Ministère des Affaires sociales et de la Santé - www.sante.gouv.fr, "Les niveaux d'alerte du Plan national canicule - Ministère des Affaires sociales et de la Santé", 2013. <http://www.sante.gouv.fr/les-niveaux-d-alerte-du-plan-national-canicule.html>

- **Level 2 - heat warning**

COMMENT: Level 2 is actually a preparatory level for possible transition to Level 3. Different services are on standby and preparing for a heatwave alert while at the same time local communication activities are targeted to inform the public of a possible heatwave, especially during weekends and holidays.

- **Level 3 - heat alert**

COMMENT: Based on the map of weather vigilance Météo-France (orange alert), the prefects of departments may trigger Level 3 - heatwave alert. The decision to trigger Level 3 - heatwave alert takes into account, where applicable, the local situation (level of pollution, population-factors such as large gatherings and others) and health indicators in line with the Regional Health Agencies (ARS). Once on Level 3, the heatwave (National Heatwave Plan) alert is activated, and the prefects of each individual department shall take all appropriate measures within the framework of the management plan of a Departmental Heatwave (GCD).³⁹

While on level 3, all regional actors are informed of the intensity and duration of the phenomenon and all other relevant information that they should be aware of. Communication is enhanced between national bodies and all individuals who might be affected by the imminent crisis reminding them to take preventative actions against it such as staying hydrated by drinking a lot of fluids and taking shelter from the heat. Plans to welcome the elderly or disabled are also set in motion raising the permanence of ambulatory care facilities, Nursing Services At Home (SSIAD) and Services to Help and Support for Home (SAAD). Activation by the mayors of municipal registers with assistance to seniors and disabled and also measures for the homeless are implemented.

- **Level 4 - Maximum mobilization**

COMMENT: On Level 4 - Maximum mobilization, which is a red weather alert, is activated by the Ministry. This level corresponds to a heatwave proved to be exceptional, very intense and durable, with the appearance of side effects in various sectors (drought, drinking water saturation hospitals or funeral, blackout, forest fires). This requires the implementation of special measures. If the crisis becomes intersectional, it requires maximum mobilization and coordination of the response of the state with the activation of the Interministerial Crisis Cell (CIC), which includes all departments⁴⁰.

Subordinate activity instantiation: Preparation for a heatwave

Subordinate activity name: Preparation in parallel with media communication

Owner: California Governor's Office of Emergency Services⁴¹, D1.2, p. 67

Activities

- Phase I - Seasonal Readiness (COMMENT: Phase I is activated during the hotter months, between May and August, and actions taken during this phase ensure the preparedness and increased readiness of the state. Specifically, actions in this phase are following:⁴²)

³⁹ Ibid.

⁴⁰ Ibid.

⁴¹ California Governor's Office of Emergency Services, "Heat", 2010.

<http://www.calema.ca.gov/planningandpreparedness/pages/heat.aspx>

⁴² Ibid.

- Initial notification of key stakeholders, such as the Departments of Food and Agriculture and of Public Health.
- Review of existing plans, procedures, and resources.
- Verification of use/availability of key facilities.
- Updating / validating notification processes.
- Initiating awareness campaigns through the media or local agencies.
- Orientation and training to plans and procedures.

Parallel activities:

- An Excessive Heat Outlook is issued by the National Weather Service (NWS) 3-7 days in advance of an event to give advance notice of the possibility of excessively hot conditions. Criteria match those of an Excessive Heat Warning. If predicted weather conditions continue to hold, an Outlook may become an Excessive Heat Watch.
- An Excessive Heat Watch is issued by the NWS 36-48 hours in advance of an event to give advance notice of the possibility of excessively hot conditions. Criteria match those of an Excessive Heat Warning.
- An Excessive Heat Warning is issued by the NWS 0-36 hours in advance of an excessive heat event that is expected to last 2 days or more.

Subordinate activity instantiation: Response to a heatwave

Subordinate activity name: Response in parallel with media communication

Owner: California Governor's Office of Emergency Services⁴³, D1.2, p. 66

Activities

- Phase II – Heat Alert (COMMENT: Various alerts can cause the activation of Phase II of the contingency plan. Specifically, heat-related special weather statements issued by either the National Weather Service or from one or more jurisdictions or credible predictions from other services concerning power outages, electrical blackouts or rotating blackouts may activate Phase II. At the same time information flow between local and state agencies is increased to support the following actions that are taken during Phase II:⁴⁴)
 - Initial coordination call and periodic or daily calls as needed among the key state agencies and the potentially affected operational areas and regions with weather and power updates.
 - Increasing public information efforts, such as releasing critical pre-scripted and public safety information and distributing excessive heat emergency pre-scripted educational materials.
 - Contacting local public health and other officials, such as the California Emergency Management Agency and the Emergency Medical Services Authority, to ensure contact with those most vulnerable to excessive heat.
 - Confirmation of roles, identify specific local needs.
 - Confirm details of agency participation, staffing.
 - Stand-by and activation (if needed) of state-owned facilities as cooling centres
 - If cooling centres are open:
 - Activation of the toll-free information number.
 - Activation of the Heatwave Web Portal to include: maps of cooling facilities with information provided by local and state agencies; general

⁴³ California Governor's Office of Emergency Services, "Heat", 2010, <http://www.calema.ca.gov/planningandpreparedness/pages/heat.aspx>

⁴⁴ Ibid.

information about measures to reduce the effects of excessive heat conditions; and links to the OA offices.

- Phase III – Heat Emergency (COMMENT: When conditions in one or more operational areas pose a severe threat Phase III is activated. Conditions may include the notification of one or more jurisdictions which have proclaimed an emergency related to excessive heat, the abnormal animal mortality due to excessive heat, the excess numbers in human medical emergencies and mortality and the extended power outages during the expected excessive heat conditions. Phase III efforts include urgent and comprehensive actions to complement and support local actions during the most severe heat event. These actions may include:⁴⁵⁾
 - Coordinating calls will increase as needed.
 - Activation of the State Operations Center (SOC).
 - Fielding requests for mutual aid and state assistance.
 - Mobilizing cooling centres.
 - The Governor may declare a state of emergency in the affected area.

Parallel activities (COMMENT: These aforementioned phases are activated based on the severity of the risk of heat to vulnerable populations, the general population, and animals. The direct involvement of state and local agencies to protect individuals increases with the severity of the risk. The plan contains specific actions to be taken by the state in each of the three phases, and a checklist to guide local actions. The specific action steps include the following:⁴⁶⁾

- Coordinating among state and local agencies (all phases).
- Disseminating information (all phases).
- Preparing cooling centres to support local response efforts (phase II).
- Activating cooling centres (phases II and III).
- Directly contacting and monitoring those at risk (phases II and III).
- Transporting those at risk to cooling centres (phases II and III).
- Governor’s proclamation of a state of emergency (phase III).

3.3.3 Societal dynamics during crises

Activity
 Activity name: Societal dynamics

Activities

- Preparation
- Response
 - Mobilisation of social support
 - Received support
 - Social embeddedness
 - Perceived support
- Recovery

Object classes acting on:

- Stakeholders

⁴⁵ Ibid.

⁴⁶ Ibid.

- Crisis
- Media

NOTES

As found in D1.1 p. 99, when help is needed the most, supporters provide it the most. Immediately after a disaster occurs, former boundaries, as between races, incomes and social classes, disappear momentarily. Terms such as ‘altruistic community’⁴⁷, ‘democracy of distress’⁴⁸, ‘heroic and honeymoon phases’⁴⁹, ‘therapeutic community’⁵⁰, ‘post-disaster utopia’⁵¹ and ‘stage of euphoria’⁵² are connected with this phase.

Although the development of social support seems to be sufficient to provide the first aid needed, it will not be sufficient in the period after the first hours. The first reason is that the need (and the expectations) for support exceeds the availability, with the consequence that victims become disillusioned because of the lack of support. When the proportion of victims to non-victims increases (one of the characteristics of natural hazards) psychological and social effects (such as stress) emerge more and more. Not only do the most vulnerable victims expect support, but so do the victims that remain relatively secure. Second, social support may not remain within a community, rather it may phase out over time. This is the period of the deterioration of support. An important factor is the disruption of the relationships within a society, caused by reasons such as death, injuries and necessary removals.⁵³ Sometimes a disaster means the end of social contacts between former neighbours. After hurricane Katrina and the flooding of New Orleans in 2005, many people were forced to move to other states in the USA. The third dislocating effect of a disaster is that social activities, and so the social cohesion, are damaged. “Simply because physical environments, settings and places instrumental for maintaining a sense of continuity and interpersonal contacts are damaged or destroyed.”⁵⁴ The feeling of being one community will reduce. Furthermore it is imaginable that within a society, conflicts arise that can be attributed to the disaster. The interpersonal relationships become more sensitive if the former standards are in stake.

It is also helpful for possibly a more detailed model to consider the finding of D1.1, p. 100, where Kaniasty and Norris summarise the different concepts that form the societal dynamics in periods around a disaster in the figure, depicted below.⁵⁵

⁴⁷ Kutak, R.I. (1938). The sociology of crises: the Louisville flood of 1937. In *Social Forces*. 17, pp. 66-72.

⁴⁸ Wallace, A. (1957). *Tornado in Worcester*. Disaster Study Number Three. Washington, DC: Committee on Disaster Studies, National Academy of Sciences: National Research Council.

⁴⁹ Wolfenstein, M. (1957). *Disaster: A Psychological Essay*. Glencoe: Free Press.

⁵⁰ Fritz, C.E. (1961). Disasters. In *Contemporary Social Problems*, R.K. Merton and R.A. Nisbet, pp. 651-694. New York: Harcourt

⁵¹ Barton, A.M. (1969). *Communities in Disaster*. Garden City, NJ: Doubleday.

⁵² Frederick, C. (1980). Effects of natural vs. human-induced violence upon victims. *Evaluation and Change, special issue*, pp. 71-75

⁵³ Kaniasty and Norris, 2004

⁵⁴ Ibid.

⁵⁵ Ibid.

Figure 7: Forming concepts for societal dynamics

3.3.4 Procedures of operation

As mentioned in the introduction, Standard Operating Procedures are models for responder organisations, which prescribe the way under which they operate. Here we show examples of such pro-active models, as well as an example of a real-time operational procedure documented in D1.2.

Activity

Activity name: Standard Operating Procedure: Attending the scene of the incident (D1.2 p. 14)

Owner: London Emergency Services Liaison Panel (LESLP), major incident procedure manual

Activities

- Preparation
 - Understand situation and determine size of incident (major or not)
 - Establish control centres
 - Issue radios to all involved
- Response
 - Secure scene and cordon off
 - Launch “Access Overload Control” scheme
 - Ensure communications are functional
 - Issue dissemination for media
- Recovery and aftermath
 - Rebuild community
 - Manage financial implications of the emergency
 - Manage the allocation and provision of resources
 - Respond to community’s welfare needs
 - Develop the internal organisation of the local authority to deal with the recovery period

Object classes involved

- Stakeholders

<p>Activity Activity name: Standard Operating Procedure: Attending the scene of the incident (D1.2 p. 22)</p> <p>Owner: Massachusetts Comprehensive Emergency Management Plan (CEMP)</p> <p>Activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pre-Impact (Preparation):: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MEMA constantly monitor for any potential events that could pose a risk. • If a potential threat is identified, MEMA will increase its readiness” by taking a series of measures (e.g., increase in monitoring activities, plans and procedures are reviewed, local, state and federal officials are briefed, communications are tested etc.) • Initial action (Response): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activation of relevant bodies and operations (e.g., State and Regional Operations Centres). • Briefing other officials • Mobilisation of resources • Continuing action (Response): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <input type="checkbox"/> Maintain communication with affected areas • Continue briefing officials • Coordinate any required need for additional assistance • <input type="checkbox"/> Initiate damage assessment teams • Demobilisation (Recovery and aftermath): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <input type="checkbox"/> Begin to release staff that are no longer required.

To describe how the police are handling communication challenges in practice, partners analysed in D1.3 a case study related to the bombing in Oslo Centre and shooting at Utøya (Norway) which took place on 22-23 July 2011. The step-by-step analysis of undertaken actions is illustrated in the table below. It gives a precise overview of “what” was done by “whom” and “when” and therefore demonstrates how the police proceeded in this type of emergency.

<p>Activity Activity name: Real Operational Procedure: Bombing in Oslo centre and shooting at Utøya, Norway⁵⁶, 22 July 2011 (D1.3 p. 51)</p> <p>Owner: Norway police force Timed sequence of activities</p>	
Time	Activity
15:13	Surveillance camera captures that Anders Behring Breivik is driving a car (with a bomb inside) into Grubbegata.
15:17	Wearing a homemade police uniform, Breivik escapes Einar Gerhardsens site and the Houses of ministries, unobstructed, waving a pistol in his right hand.
15:25	A car bomb explodes in Grubbegata, Government quarter. The explosion

⁵⁶ Sources: www.tv2.no, www.dt.no; www.nrk.no

	occurs between the building where the Prime minister's office is located and the Department of Justice and R4, which houses the Oil- and Energy Ministry and the Ministry of Industry and trade ⁵⁷ .
15:26	The police in Oslo receive the first message about the explosion. Two minutes later the first police patrol arrives, immediately making a large intervention in the city centre.
15:30	Armed Forces Special Command mobilises their Command Centre.
15:32	The police logs that a security guard saw a person running from a white van before the explosion.
15:32	The head of the Government's Crisis-Advisory Board, Morten Ruud, is formally notified by the Crisis Support Unit on the explosion.
15:34	Head of health and a medical unit is established in the VG-building (a building where the newspaper VG is located).
15:41	Police helicopter crew calls the Oslo police district and offers to come to work.
16:00	Liaison between the Military/Defense and the Oslo Police District establishes.
16:40	A man in a police uniform – Anders Behring Breivik – parks a civilian car – a Fiat Doblo – at the Mainland Utvika in Tyrifjorden.
16:45	A Sea King helicopter takes off from Rygge.
16:47	The Police emergency squad contacts the closest Air Force base which is set up with hellos (Rygge) to check availability of the military's Bell-helicopters.
16:53	A Sea King-helicopter is sent from Ørland main air station with bomb experts.
16:57	The Captain on the MS Thorbjørn (The Utøya ferry) is notified that a policeman wants transport to Utøya.
17:00	The police confirm that the explosion in the Governments quarter is a bomb.
17:00	The Air Force base Crisis centre is mobilized at Rygge.
17:04	The Ferry MS Thorbjørnsails from the Mainland to Utøya with Anders Behring Breivik on board as a passenger.
17:08	Breivik chasing young people at the AUF-camp on Utøya and kills those who gets in his way.
17:09	A Sea King helicopter lands on Voldsløkka in Oslo, ready to transport victims to hospitals outside Oslo if necessary.
17:24	The Emergency Medical Communication Centre (EMCC) at Vestre Viken Regional health authorities receives the first message about the shooting on Utøya.
17:27	Message about the shooting on Utøya to Nordre Buskerud Police-district.
17:28	EMCC Oslo/Akershus is notified about the shooting on Utøya of relatives through the Health Emergency Number 113. The message is confirmed immediately by EMCC Buskerud. EMCC Buskerud controls the medical assistance with support from EMCC Oslo/Akershus.
17:30	The Police in Oslo receive the first message about the shooting.
17:31	The Police Emergency Squad Delta drives towards Utøya.
17:38	The police in Northern Buskerudask the Oslo police for assistance.
17:41	First message on the community of Twitter: <i>"There is shooting going on at Utøya, my little sister is there and called home now."</i>
17:42	The first ambulance helicopter takes off.
17:48	New message on Twitter: <i>"There's a shootout on Utøya. The Labor Party youth summer camp is to be evacuated. Complete chaos. Police is on the way. "</i>
17:52	The first police patrol arrives from Buskerud arrives at Utstranda from on the

⁵⁷ The main fire-station is located in the Government quarter. Windows were blown in by the pressure wave, and it took some time before fire-engines from here could come out. Fire engines from other stations, however, were relegated.

	shore of Tyrifjorden.
17:52	Kjetil Vevle, Central Executive Committee member of the AUF, on Twitter: "Somebody is shooting at Utøya. Update the police!! " .
17:55	The quay at Utvika is formally cleared.
17:57	The first ambulance arrives at Utvika.
17:58	The Joint Rescue Coordination Centre receives notification about the Utøya-shooting from EMCC-Oslo/Akershus.
18:00	The first Bell-helicopter is ready to take off from Rygge, according to the military's operational headquarters.
18:01	Breivik is connected in an emergency phone call.
18:03	The police receive confirmation that "a suitable boat" for the police action is on the way.
18:05	The first patrol from the local police arrives at the pier where the boat Utøya settles from.
18:09	The emergency squad from the Oslo police unites with the local police on the scene.
18:21	The military/defense receives a request from the police for help from Armed Forces Special Command.
18:25	Crew from the emergency squad arrives at Utøya by boat from a pier located 3.6 miles away. During the trip to Utøya the motor of the small and overcrowded boat stops.
18:26	Breiviks' phone call to the police.
18:27	The perpetrator is called by the police. He surrenders and is put in handcuffs. He was previously unknown to the police, but has been convicted for a minor road traffic offence.
18:30	Ambulance personnel are on standby to descend on Utøya. They are told to not continue onto the island, because it is unclear whether shooting is still in progress.
18:50	Evacuation of patients from the quay at Utvikastarts after clearance of the area by local police.
18:55	The first Bell-helicopter takes off from Rygge.
19:00	The situation is chaotic and the police have no overview. Police urge people in Oslo to remain at home and use cellular networks as little as possible. Police helicopter crew is instructed back to work.
19:20	A physician, an operating Manager, and a paramedic, all from Oslo/Akershus arrives as the first health care personnel on Utøya.
19:20	The other Bell-helicopter takes off from Rygge, en route to Utøya.
19:30	Police confirms that seven were killed at the bomb explosion in the Government quarter.
Approx 19:45	The Bell-helicopter arrives at Utøya.
20:00	Norway receives support statements from heads of States all over the world. Foreign media is showing great interest of the incident.
21:57	Advice from National Guard, the object protection Oslo, granted.
22:00	His Majesty the King's Guard assistance request granted. 700 troops were ready at 22-23, soldiers in place on the object protection Saturday morning.
23:20	Police gives a press conference and state that the person arrested is an ethnic Norwegian man.
23:29	Undetonated explosives are found on Utøya.
Just before midnight	The police are taking action against Breiviks apartment at Skøyen in western Oslo.

4 IT TOOL AIDED MODEL

The model of crisis concepts of the previous chapter was coded using a well known IT tool for UML modelling, namely the **Enterprise Architect**.⁵⁸ Enterprise Architect is a visual modelling and design tool based on OMG’s UML. The tool supports design and construction of software systems and modelling of business processes and industry based domains.

The model codified along this platform includes a class diagram and an activity diagram. In our model the class diagram contains the Crisis, Media and Stakeholders classes. Each class is the blueprint from which individual objects, i.e. instances of a class can be created. Each object has its own data but its underlying structure is defined by the class.

Since we view Crisis as an object, our model was built so as to show the interdependence among the object classes. To this end, we created public attributes of all classes and assigned them to each other, as needed. In general, the relationship between classes is shown by an arrow, which points at the class that provides one or more attributes.

Each class has unique methods. Methods are collections of statements that are grouped together to perform an operation. Such methods enable communication among classes so that attributes or objects are sent and received. Methods thus constitute the communication channel between classes and the rest of the “world” and, correspondingly, objects constitute the messages transferred.

The Activity Diagram of the model can be likened to a hierarchical virtual tree, with every part representing a different activity. Despite the diversity, all activities are characterised by the same structure. Each activity has a start symbol “●”, where the arrows begin, as well as an end symbol “⊗”, where the arrows stop.

The first diagram shown in the model, depicts the organisations and the procedures taking place when crises occur. Most of the activities have interior activities called “children-activities”. For example the activity “Response” of Societal Dynamics, contains the “Mobilization of social support” activity. In that event, “Response” is the “father-activity” of the “Mobilization of social support” activity. The last activity, in turn, contains three more activities called “Received support”, “Social Embeddedness” and “Perceived Support”. In this event “Mobilization of social support” becomes a “father-activity”. This example shows how an activity can behave at once as “father” and “child”.

“Children- activities”, are executed when their “father-activity” is activated. In diagrams where many “father-activities” exist, the next “father-activity” waits until all “children-activities” of the previous one, have been executed. For example, the “Recovery” activity shown in the figure above, waits until “Mobilization of social support”, “Received support”, “Social Embeddedness” and “Perceived Support” have ended. Sometimes though, activities must be executed in parallel. In such cases, we add the symbol “█”, named “Fork/Join”, placed between the start and the activities that will participate in parallel execution. An arrow begins from the “start” symbol and ends on the Fork/Join symbol, from which the arrows of the parallel activities begin. In order for the concurrent execution to be secured, a

⁵⁸ Enterprise Architect tool, Sparx Systems Pty Ltd., 2000-2014, <http://www.sparxsystems.com/products/ea/index.html>

Fork/Join symbol is also placed between the activities and the “end” symbol. This completes the correct end of the flow.

Figure 8. Example of “father” and “child” activities

Figure 9. Example of parallel execution.

Last but not least, we ran simulations to ensure the consistency of the Activity Diagram. As pointed out in the Enterprise Architect guide:

“Simulating models offers several benefits by helping you to:

- Gain a better understanding of how a model actually works at run-time
- Validate that your behavioral models describe the correct process or event flow
- Identify potential bottlenecks, inefficiencies and other problems in your system model
- Detect errors early in the development cycle – prior to committing resources for implementation.”

4.1 CLASS DIAGRAMS

The class diagrams of our model as implemented in the tool are shown below as a single diagram showing all three classes accompanied by separate diagrams for each class.

Figure 10. Class diagram showing the three classes Crisis, Stakeholders, Media and interdependencies

Figure 11. Class diagram showing the class Crisis and interdependencies

Figure 12. Class diagram showing the class Media and interdependencies

Figure 13. Class diagram showing the class Stakeholders and interdependencies

4.2 ACTIVITY DIAGRAMS

Activity diagrams are representative of time evolution (dynamics). They follow the design of chapter 2.

Figure 14. High level activity diagram

4.2.1 Individual dynamics during crises

Figure 15. Activity: “Individual dynamics” (see section 3.3.1)

Figure 16. Subordinate activity: “Warning”

4.2.2 Organisational dynamics during crises

The next diagrams show the activities for “Organizational Dynamics” along with examples of instantiations, as applied by various national authorities for various types of crisis.

Figure 17. Activity diagram for “Organizational Dynamics” and example instantiations of the preparation activity, such as earthquake preparation, general preparation for crisis and preparation for flood, by national authorities of Greece, Italy and France correspondingly (section 3.3.2)

Figure 18. Instantiation of activity: “Organizational Dynamics” at Standard Operating Procedure level, by the response plan “Xenokratis” of the national authorities of Greece. The plan includes high level descriptions of all subordinate activities for preparation, response and recovery (section 3.3.2)

Figure 19. Instantiation of the activity “Preparation” for specific types of crisis (heatwave) by national authorities of France (section 3.3.2)

Figure 20. Instantiation of the activity “Preparation” for specific types of crisis (heatwave) by national authorities of the US, in California in phase I (section 3.3.2)

Figure 22. Instantiation of activity: “Preparation” for a specific type of crisis (heatwave) by national authorities of the US in California in phase III (section 3.3.2)

Figure 23. Instantiation of activity: “Organizational Dynamics” for Emergent Groups and of the corresponding subordinate activity “Response” (section 3.3.2)

4.2.3 Societal Dynamics during crises

The qualitative part of this dynamics has been described in Deliverable D1.1, where it is also shown that an interdependency also exists among concepts such as “status and assets”

“received support”, “perceived support”, “severity of exposure” and “emotional distress” (also see Figure 7 of section 2 in this document). It is therefore not a straightforward matter to produce a model of organisational dynamics, not only due to sheer complexity but also due to the considerable semantic richness of concepts such as those above. Using conventional terminology-based semantic models such as ontologies can offer help, but this can be limited due to the lack of an as yet commonly accepted set of terms to describe societal dynamics.

What we show below is a high level activity (process) model of societal dynamics as described in D1.1.

Figure 24. Activity: “Societal Dynamics” and subordinate activities “Response” and “Mobilization of social support” (section 3.3.3)

4.2.4 Examples of Standard Operating Procedures

We show examples of activities as realised by response organisations.

Figure 25. Instantiation of activity: “Standard Operating Procedure” for the procedure “Attending the scene of the incident” and its subordinate activities, as realised by the Massachusetts Comprehensive Emergency Management Plan (CEMP) (section 3.3.4)

Figure 26. Instantiation of activity: “Standard Operating Procedure” for the procedure “Attending the scene of the incident” and its subordinate activities, as realised by the London Emergency Services Liaison Panel (LESLP), major incident procedure manual (section 3.3.4)

5 COMMUNICATIONS CHALLENGES AND PROCESSES

Communications challenges in crises are abundant in various forms and have been analysed by the partners in many parts of COSMIC. Communication also affects the course of the crisis itself and its impact. The difficulty is however that it is not a well-defined process which is amenable to modelling. In what follows, we have isolated the tabulated challenges and prescribed processes for communication during crises, as they appear in D1.3 pp. 20-31, which may form part of a model, although, at this stage, we are not able to express those in a consistent semi formal way resembling that of the previous chapter.

5.1 UNDERSTANDING OF DISASTER MANAGEMENT AMONG THE PUBLIC

Title:	Understanding of disaster management among the public
Background	
<p>The public are imperative actors in disaster response through a variety of roles. When disaster strikes, it will affect population carrying out significant relief efforts, both independently and in support of the first responders’ organisations. The public also plays a major role in preparatory phases, for example as a source of funding. However, more importantly, the legitimacy of official relief agencies derives from the support of the public. An adequate understanding of disaster management will allow the public to play these roles efficiently and efficiently, therefore strengthening overall disaster management capacity.</p>	
Improvement opportunity:	
<p>Develop tools and solutions that promote better understanding among the public about:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Risks and how they can be mitigated - The characteristics of disasters - How to act in different types of disaster - How the public can support the authorities in disaster situations <p>Develop tools and solutions that promote better understanding with the public about how response agencies work, for example with respect to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policy choices - Training needs and volunteer policies - Funding needs for different types of activities 	
Constraints:	
<p>The fact that the legitimacy of public agencies relies on public support needs to be taken into consideration. The public as such is not homogenous, as it is a group of different communities with different backgrounds, cultures, interests, perceptions, etc., which require tailored information.</p>	
The opportunity from different perspectives	
<i>Procedures and organisation:</i>	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop procedures to effectively engage with the public in preparatory activities, including the identification of the appropriate levels of engagement, with regards to risks associated with such engagement (Red Cross USA⁵⁹) - Social media listening tools (2012 opening of a digital operations centre for humanitarian relief) - Develop procedures for educating and informing the public
<i>Personnel:</i>
Identify training needs
<i>Technology:</i>
Provide dissemination and presentation tools and platforms
Provide tools that support public participation in training and exercises

5.2 EVOLVED MANAGEMENT OF INFORMATION TO THE MEDIA AND THE PUBLIC

Title:	Evolved management of information to the media and the public
Background	
<p>Reaching out to the public can be an important aspect of CM activities. The purpose of interaction might be to allow people to support the response, to calm people, to avoid interference with the response effort, to minimize the inquiries to active responders, or to encourage desirable behaviour. The media plays an important role in this process, and without active management the information flow from the CM to the public, the situation can become unpredictable and unreliable. This effect has been reinforced by the evolution of the media in the last decade towards a more social, distributed and participative character. Management of the media includes both monitoring the current reporting, to discover possible inaccuracies or misinformation, as well as active provision of information. The management of information with the media and the public has an intrinsic cross-agency character, since conflicting information coming from different agencies can cause serious problems.</p>	
Improvement opportunity:	
<p>Improve the ability of CM to assure effective flows of validated, balanced information to the public.</p>	
Constraints:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Democratic aspects of the government/media relation must be taken into account - Privacy aspects must be taken into account - Cultural or social differences between countries and regions should be taken into account <p>Significant research is already available within this area, and COSMIC should take into account the latest developments when preparing the corresponding guidelines.</p>	
The opportunity from different perspectives	
<i>Procedures and organisation:</i>	

⁵⁹ <http://breakinggov.com/2012/03/07/red-cross-launches-social-media-ops-center-for-humanitarian-reli/>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Develop agreed (both between agencies and with the media) procedures for media management, including responsibilities, development of information packages and management of dissemination channels – Develop methods and procedures for media monitoring
<i>Personnel:</i>
Identify training needs for public relation (PR) / media relation personnel
<i>Technology:</i>
Provide suitable technical means to distribute information to the public. This could include the use of mobile networks, social media and other forms of information infrastructure. Provide technical means to support the media management process
Related opportunities:
Better understanding of disaster response among the public, Volunteer Management ⁶⁰ .

5.3 EARLY WARNING CAPABILITIES

Title:	Early warning capabilities
Background	
<p>In most disasters, time is a critical factor and the earlier response can commence, the less difficult the operation will be. To be able to use response assets as effectively and efficiently as possible makes it increasingly important to obtain warning and information about oncoming crises as early as possible.</p> <p>Early warning will provide better conditions for the response to any disaster, but it is of particular importance in disasters that can be prevented or mitigated by early intervention, such as forest fires.</p>	
Improvement opportunity:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improve prediction capabilities of different disasters, particularly those where early warning can help prevent the disaster or minimise its consequences, such as fires. - Improve the early detection of oncoming disasters - Improve dissemination of disaster alerts and the cooperation between agencies and between agencies and scientific institutes (Hydrology, Seismology etc.) 	
Constraints:	
There are numerous early warning systems already in place, both overarching and relating to specific disaster types. Duplication of these should be avoided.	
The opportunity from different perspectives	
<i>Procedures and organisation:</i>	
<p>Develop methods that allow for early detection or prediction of disasters</p> <p>Develop mechanisms for the dissemination of early warnings</p>	
<i>Personnel:</i>	
Methods need to be supported by adequate training	
<i>Technology:</i>	

⁶⁰ See Chapter 5 for more information.

<p>Develop tools supporting prediction or detection</p> <p>Develop tools that support dissemination of early warnings</p>

5.4 ACQUISITION OF INFORMATION FROM EXTERNAL SOURCES

Title:	Acquisition of information from external sources
Background	
<p>Command, coordination and awareness in disaster management require information from a range of sources. Key assets are, of course, the resources available of the different first responder organisations, both human and technical ones. However, the importance of external information resources is constantly growing (e.g., the press, the population in an area, or the public at the scene of the disaster area). Social networks, cellular networks, catalogues such as yellow pages, photo and video “crowd sourcing”, the respective social media, and (local) government databases providers are other examples of such sources. The main point is the requirement of a solid information management system.</p>	
Improvement opportunity:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Understand the ways to quickly access information from relevant sources for CM, – Provide means to analyse, categorise and draw conclusions from these sources. <p>Systematic gathering of information from social networks is one example. A potential application of this is to gain knowledge about sentiments. Another example is the information available in cellular network which can be used for instance to monitor mass movement of people. Data from these sources should be used both operationally and for after-action evaluation. Integrate “Big Data” applications into the crisis management procedures.</p>	
Constraints:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Ethical concerns exist with the systematic gathering of personal information (“big data”) or the use of information sources which are sensitive from an integrity point of view. – The possibility of malicious or accidental insertion of misinformation should be taken into account. 	
The opportunity from different perspectives	
<i>Procedures and organisation:</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Develop methodology – Develop procedures for the interaction with data owners to gain access to their data – Develop procedures for managing ethical concerns with respect to data gathering. 	
<i>Personnel:</i>	
Tools and methods will require adequate training	
<i>Technology:</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Find technical means to connect to adequate data sources – Develop means to systematize and analyse data / “big data” – Cross media analysis 	

5.5 EFFICIENT WAYS TO GATHER DATA FROM RESPONDERS

Title:	Efficient ways to gather data from responders
Background	
Getting quality data from first responder organisations is critical both for the command and coordination in the relief phase and for subsequent evaluation. At the same time, responders are often already overloaded with the operational task at hand, and putting further burden on them in the form of requirements to provide data is often not possible. There is therefore a need to find ways to automatically or with minimized burden on the acting first responder in the field to gather necessary information, while still assuring that it has the adequate quality and is appropriately structures. (Shared situation awareness is a necessary enabler for communication common understanding).	
Improvement opportunity:	
1) Develop guidelines addressing how to effectively gather data on the operation, resources, their location and condition, communications, decisions, etc. This could include extraction of data from different operational systems or the use of different kinds of sensors. 2) Develop methodology that allows for easy gathering of information, while putting minimal burden on the first responders.	
Constraints:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Privacy concerns must be taken into account - Solutions must put minimal burden on first responders - Security concerns must be taken into account - For use in external operations, solutions should not require continuous access to energy 	
The opportunity from different perspectives	
<i>Procedures and organisation:</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information needs should be clearly identified - Procedures for gathering information, including priorities, should be developed - Procedures for the management of data should be identified 	
<i>Personnel:</i>	
Procedures should be enriched.	
<i>Technology:</i>	
Develop solutions that automatically gather relevant data Develop solutions that aid easy gathering of structured data at operational and tactical levels Develop solutions that gather data without exhausting first responder equipment’s energy	

5.6 VOLUNTEER MANAGEMENT

Title:	Volunteer management
Background	

In any crisis, volunteers will offer to provide help to the relief operation. They may do so through organisations dedicated for this purpose but also by offering their help on-scene or even starting their own effort in parallel. Volunteers are an asset with significant potential to support disaster management, but also potentially delaying or disturbing the operation or even carrying out harmful actions. It is usually the role of the crisis management structure to manage these groups.
Improvement opportunity:
Develop procedures for the management of volunteers, particularly spontaneous volunteers that will harvest the potential of this important asset. Aspects to be taken into account should include the planning of volunteer work, communication with the public about needed and not needed volunteers, risks associated with engaging volunteers, ethical and social aspects connected with the use or non-use of volunteers.
Constraints:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Legal responsibility needs to be taken into account - Cultural factors need to be taken into account - Different types of volunteerism (individual, spontaneous, organised, upon request) may require significantly different solutions.
The opportunity from different perspectives
<i>Procedures and organisation:</i>
Tested procedures for volunteer management should be developed.
<i>Personnel:</i>
Possible training for organised volunteers should be assessed and if required, curriculums could be developed and improved education for the “interested public” should be sought
<i>Technology:</i>
Technical means could support communication with the public with respect to volunteering

5.7 HARMONIZATION OF LANGUAGE AND TERMINOLOGY

Title:	Harmonization of language and terminology
Background	
<p>Collaborative preparation, execution and assessment of disaster response become significantly more difficult if the crisis management structure and the first responder organisations involved do not use the same terminology.</p> <p>At the same time, language and terminology is affected by the cultural and social context, and attempts to over-standardize may result in terminology that is not rich enough to be applicable in all relevant situations.</p>	
Improvement opportunity:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify what the priority areas are where a common terminology is needed in order to ensure effectiveness of cross-agency or cross-border collaboration - Develop and devise activities (dedicated exercises etc.) that support the harmonisation of terminology or the mutual understanding of different terminology. - Develop standard terminology in priority areas and further build on research conducted in other sectors for translation of information in case of cross-border cooperation - Develop tools and mechanisms to support the dissemination and implementation of common terminology 	

Constraints:
Existing efforts (also from other FP projects) should be taken into account Cultural differences need to be taken into account The lack of means to enforce terminology should be taken into account
The opportunity from different perspectives
<i>Procedures and organisation:</i> Map and systematise current efforts within language and terminology harmonisation Develop standardized terminology in priority areas
<i>Personnel:</i> Identify suitable training, including cross-agency and cross-country training, in support of standardised terminology
<i>Technology:</i> Develop technical support to the development, use and management of terminology standards

5.8 SHARING AND IMPLEMENTING LESSONS AND BEST PRACTICES

Title:	Sharing and implementing lessons and best practices
Background	
<p>Lessons based on experience from past missions, together with exercise outcomes, are some of the most important sources of knowledge to develop the disaster relief capacity. Analysing and collecting such lessons can form the basis for identification of best practices, which can guide work of the complete disaster management community.</p> <p>A key problem in exploiting this knowledge is that it is primarily carried out by those who take part in the operation or exercise, and that each individual carries only a fragmented picture of the full operation.</p> <p>Other issues concern the dissemination of lessons and practices across agency and country borders. Furthermore, they must make sure they are implemented and stimulate improvement, as well as look at possible measures for a successful implementation and the potential impact on an organisation’s performance.</p>	
Improvement opportunity:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide mechanisms and supporting tools for identifying, analysing, sharing, disseminating and implementing lessons from operations and exercises. - Provide mechanisms and support tools for developing, validation and implementing best practices in different domains of disaster management⁶¹ 	

⁶¹ See: Use of social media in crisis communication, found atL: http://www.kortom.be/file_uploads/5069.pdf
and FBI social media criteria for Law Enforcement Use, found at: <http://www.fbi.gov/stats-services/publications/law-enforcement-bulletin/2013/february/social-media-establishing-criteria-for-law-enforcement-use>

Constraints:
<p>Sharing of lessons can expose vulnerabilities or weaknesses, which may cause agencies to be hesitant towards this.</p> <p>Experience shows that more databases do not automatically lead to more and effective dissemination of “lessons learned” or to an effective implementation. Though incident and exercise reports are collected widely, the data compiled is typically structured differently from agency to agency and country to country, considerably handicapping any attempt to identify and share similar lessons and practices across agencies and borders, further complicated through different terminologies and languages used.</p>
The opportunity from different perspectives
<i>Procedures and organisation:</i>
<p>Identifying, sharing and implementing “lessons learned” will require a common process, including.</p> <p>Gathering of appropriate data, analysis, dissemination, implementation and evaluation. Processes for validating and agreeing on best practices, across agency and country borders are required. Best practices should stimulate the development of future polices.</p>
<i>Personnel:</i>
This opportunity is essentially about efficiently improving personnel communication skills.
<i>Technology:</i>
<p>Technology could support all phases of the lessons learned process, perhaps most importantly the gathering of data, the analysis and the dissemination.</p> <p>Technology could support the evaluation and implementation of best practices, for example through supporting gaming activities that are used to evaluate and implement practices.</p>

5.9 INTERAGENCY INFORMATION SHARING

Title:	Interagency information sharing
Background	
<p>Information exchange between agencies, which is important both in the preparatory and the operational phases, is currently hampered by a lack of procedures, lack of interoperable information formats and a lack of systematic information management in many agencies.</p>	
Improvement opportunity:	
<p>Develop practices (and tools) which support first responders and disaster managers to identify relevant information, make its content and form sharable, publish and disseminate it and make it possible for other stakeholders to effectively receive it.</p> <p>Information sharing is required both in the preparation, the response and the recovery phases, and at several levels of management.</p>	
Constraints:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Although improvement needs still remain, there are a number of existing initiatives which need to be taken into account. - Standardisation efforts and process development must take into account the heterogeneous structure of disaster management, especially for international relief. - Integrity and information security issues must be taken into account. 	
The opportunity from different perspectives	

<i>Procedures and organisation:</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Identify appropriate procedures and context-based information sharing schemes. – Map available information standards and if necessary, develop new one.
<i>Personnel:</i>
Identify suitable training needs connected to information sharing practices and tools
<i>Technology:</i>
Provide technical tools and best-practice guidelines that support inter-agency information sharing. This could include dissemination support tools, information gateways, wrappers, accessible repositories and other means.

5.10 RESPONDER COMMUNICATIONS IN REMOTE AREAS

Title:	Responder communications in remote areas
Background	
While response communications within most parts of the EU territory are fairly well-developed (though some challenges may remain), the situation in remote areas (which could be outside the EU or certain areas inside the EU) is not always satisfactory. In such situations, one needs to rely on local infrastructure or commercial networks, which may be limited to begin with and further damaged by the disaster or congested, or on portable solutions that tend to be limited in bandwidth and reliability.	
Improvement opportunity:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide better / alternative in-field communications methods, both inside the first responder’s and crisis management agencies and cross-agency/ cross-border - Provide better communications methods from the scene of the disaster to central agencies. 	
Constraints:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Tampere convention should be respected⁶² - Access to power in the disaster area may be limited 	
The opportunity from different perspectives	
<i>Procedures and organisation:</i>	
Procedures and agreements that optimize the use of available bandwidth and frequencies should be developed.	
<i>Personnel:</i>	
Awareness on the limitations in capacity and the consequences of overuse should be created All equipment needs to be provided together with appropriate training.	
<i>Technology:</i>	
Appropriate technical communications solutions should be developed	

5.11 RETENTION OF INFORMATION AND LOG-KEEPING

⁶² Tampere Convention on the Provision of Telecommunication Resources for Disaster Mitigation and Relief Operations. found at: <http://www.ifrc.org/Docs/idrl/I271EN.pdf>

Title:	Retention of information and log-keeping
Background	
<p>A vast amount of information is generated in all phases of disaster relief. In the preparatory phase, information is generated on capacities, stocks, organisations, training, or capabilities, etc., which needs to be used in the response phase. In the response phase, flows of relief goods, funds and people need to be captured and stored to allow for evaluation, providing the basis for future preparation.</p>	
Improvement opportunity:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide means/guidelines to warehouse information that allows for easy access across agencies, while still respecting needs for security and privacy, supporting disaster management preparation, response and evaluation - Provide means / guidelines on how to automatically log relevant information pertaining to the execution of the operation and/or supports commanders’ manual log-keeping. This should include the relevant information on decisions and actions taken, use of different assets, the flow of goods, the tasks and whereabouts of responders and other kinds of operational information. 	
Constraints:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information is generated in many different forms and within many different systems that will continue to live for a long time (legacy systems). - Information generated is often unstructured - Privacy and information security concerns must be taken into account - Willingness to share information can be low, which should be mitigated through solutions - Several solutions already exist, both within agencies and cross-agencies (Relief Web etc). New solutions must expand or leverage these. 	
The opportunity from different perspectives	
<i>Procedures and organisation:</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop principles for information warehousing in terms of what should be retained, where it should be retained, who should be able to access it etc. - Develop procedures for information warehousing 	
<i>Personnel:</i>	
Identify training needs related to information warehousing and develop suitable course curriculums and training material	
<i>Technology:</i>	
Develop technology that supports information warehousing in distributed, non-centralised organisations. Develop technology that allows for information gathering and log-keeping	

5.12 PSYCHO-SOCIAL SUPPORT – INTERVENTION STRATEGIES

Title:	Psycho-social support – intervention strategies
Background	

Affected public and crisis responders have to deal with different forms of stress and other psycho-social strains and traumata; in order to reduce the short-, mid- and long term consequences of the various forms of stress and psycho-social strains, psychosocial support should be provided in a timely and professional way, including the Health Services themselves.
Improvement opportunity:
- Effective intervention strategies and related support should be developed.
Constraints:
The challenge is to provide acceptable psychological and psychosocial support to the affected public and the Health Care teams, which also could suffer from the traumatic effects of the incident.
The opportunity from different perspectives
<i>Procedures and organisation:</i>
- Develop principles and methodology for identification of different actors which are in need of psycho-social support.
<i>Personnel:</i>
Identify training needs related to psycho-social support and develop suitable course curricula and training material.

5.13 COORDINATION CHALLENGES

Title:	Coordination challenges
Background	
The hosting capability of each hospital is provided through a contingency plan provided to the civil protection and stating, in addition to other information, the number of red codes casualties that could be hosted in case of emergency.	
The possibility to have run-time updated information on hospitals hosting capabilities would put the decision-makers in a better position to carry out a more effective casualty regulation.	
Large scale disasters and emergency situations expose the lack of integration and collaboration among health care services revealing challenges for effective Decision Support Systems (DSS) ⁶³ .	
Improvement opportunity:	
Develop procedures for the management of hospitals hosting capabilities.	
Constraints:	

⁶³ Pine, J. C., “Wiley Pathways Technology in Emergency Management”, John Wiley and Sons, Hoboken, NJ, 2007; Rao, J. E., “Improving Disaster Management: The Role of IT in Mitigation, Preparedness, Response, and Recovery”, Committee on Using Information Technology to Enhance Disaster Management, National Research Council, Washington, DC, 2007, National Academies Press.

Projects conducted in various European countries on a national basis, but also financed through FP6 and FP7 projects are developing or have developed working prototypes of applications to assist communication and information management in the aftermath of disasters. These applications target tasks, includes disaster scene management (particularly triage), remote monitoring of the condition of victims, transmission of medical images for various purposes including remote diagnosis and identification of victims (via dental records, for example), and decision support. Nonetheless, a recent review of such applications indicates that still, most of the applications rely on paper-based methods to collect information⁶⁴.

Furthermore, an obstacle in the utilisation of such applications pertains to the difficulty of mastering their use. This becomes an important issue particularly when the applications are only utilised for rare emergency situations. As such, developing a more comprehensive understanding of user requirements, involving users in the design stage of decision support systems, and promoting more consistent use of such systems can make an important contribution to their efficacy at times of emergencies⁶⁵.

The opportunity from different perspectives

Procedures and organisation:

Currently decisions concerning contingency planning, procedures effectiveness and casualty regulations are made on the basis of experience, statistical data and live simulations. There is a strong need for decision support aids, especially for:

- Contingency Planning
- New procedures/doctrines evaluation
- Casualty Regulation, i.e. which casualty should be sent to which hospital

⁶⁴ Case, T, C. Morrison and A. Vuylsteke, “The Clinical Application of Mobile Technology to Disaster Medicine”, *Prehospital and Disaster Medicine*, Vol. 27, Issue 5, 2012, pp. 473–80.

⁶⁵ Case, T, C. Morrison and A. Vuylsteke, “The Clinical Application of Mobile Technology to Disaster Medicine”, *Prehospital and Disaster Medicine*, Vol. 27, Issue 5, 2012, pp. 473–80.; Kindsmüller, M, T. Mentler, M. Herczeg et al. “*Care & Prepare– Usability_Engineering for Mass Casualty Incidents*”, ACM EICS4Med 2011: Proceedings of the 1st International Workshop on Engineering Interactive Computing Systems for Medicine and Health Care, 2011, pp. 30-35.

6 CONCLUSION

Crises and their complex dynamics are not directly amenable to modelling. This is made worse by their time-continuous nature as opposed to the discrete one assumed by most enterprise modelling methods and architectures. Despite these difficulties, there is value in modelling crises; IT tools produced can help evaluate scenarios of possible action via simulation and select semi-optimal options among various alternatives.

Our findings show that, besides the dynamic component, crisis management also involves a considerable static, i.e. not changing in time, component. This is because the actors involved in a crisis are relatively well-defined: response organisations with known structure and hierarchies, equipment of varying functionality, different forms of infrastructure and people under relatively known social organisation schemes. These structures are amenable to semantic modelling aiming at the creation of uniform terminologies and dictionaries, thus directly benefiting semantic interoperability and integration among relevant IT systems and tools. Indeed, as our studies show, relevant research has resulted in a number of ontologies such as: MOAC, which conforms to de-facto standards developed by the Inter Agency Standing Committee (IASC), the Emergency Shelter Cluster in Haiti, the 3W database and the Ushahidi Haiti Project, thus having a direct link with social media; and HXL, the Humanitarian eXchange Language, supported by the UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA). To those one could add the European developed DiRes ontology, which describes emergency and disaster events, and the key factors associated with disaster response activities.

Regarding the dynamic component of crises, process models, ideally combined with semantic models, are used. These are also contained in the specifications of methods such as ISyCri and MOAC, which were originally described only as ontologies. Descriptions of models here are in need of a modelling language such as the general purpose UML or the crisis management oriented CEML (Crisis and Emergency Modelling Language).

For the purposes of modelling the concepts used by COSMIC in WP1, we have utilised the findings of deliverables D1.1, D1.2 and D1.3 to formulate a model/typology of crises and the associated high level actions. Given that the creation of an all encompassing model of a crisis is generally not feasible, at least within the resources and mandate of a Support Action such as COSMIC, we have offered a high level description of the features and dynamics of crises as described in WP1, based on UML.

At the present stage of the model, we have confined ourselves to objects and object classes, stakeholders (actors, a special class of objects), and activities. The aim was to offer abstractions for selected parts of the material of WP1 which depict structure (via object classes and objects) and behaviour (via activities) during crises. The initial idea in this deliverable is to view a crisis as an object in an object-oriented environment. Starting from our main interest, a CRISIS is a class of objects which can be described by common characteristics and parameters (attributes), and which, upon assignment of specific values to these attributes, can generate its various specific objects, such as: the Katrina Hurricane, the Boston Bombings, the Heat Wave in France and so on, as studied in WP1.

We have isolated the most important activities related to crises as presented in WP1. The so constructed high level model was subsequently coded using a UML compliant IT tool

(Enterprise Architect) so as to check consistency and to provide a uniform way of presentation.

Finally, we have isolated the tabulated challenges and prescribed processes for communication during crises, as they appear in our deliverables, which may form part of a future model, although, at this stage, we are not able to express those in a consistent semi-formal way.